

A RISC-V in-network accelerator for flexible high-performance low-power packet processing

Salvatore Di Girolamo^{*}, Andreas Kurth[†], Alexandru Calotoiu^{*}, Thomas Benz[†], Timo Schneider^{*},
Jakub Beránek[‡], Luca Benini[†], Torsten Hoeffler^{*}

^{*}Dept. of Computer Science, ETH Zürich, Switzerland

[†]Integrated System Laboratory, ETH Zürich, Switzerland

[‡]IT4Innovations, VŠB - Technical University of Ostrava

*{first.lastname}@inf.ethz.ch, †{first.lastname}@iis.ee.ethz.ch, ‡jakub.beranek@vsb.cz

Abstract—The capacity of offloading data and control tasks to the network is becoming increasingly important, especially if we consider the faster growth of network speed when compared to CPU frequencies. In-network compute alleviates the host CPU load by running tasks directly in the network, enabling additional computation/communication overlap and potentially improving overall application performance. However, sustaining bandwidths provided by next-generation networks, e.g., 400 Gbit/s, can become a challenge. sPIN is a programming model for in-NIC compute, where users specify handler functions that are executed on the NIC, for each incoming packet belonging to a given message or flow. It enables a CUDA-like acceleration, where the NIC is equipped with lightweight processing elements that process network packets in parallel. We investigate the architectural specialties that a sPIN NIC should provide to enable high-performance, low-power, and flexible packet processing. We introduce PsPIN, a first open-source sPIN implementation, based on a multi-cluster RISC-V architecture and designed according to the identified architectural specialties. We investigate the performance of PsPIN with cycle-accurate simulations, showing that it can process packets at 400 Gbit/s for several use cases, introducing minimal latencies (26 ns for 64 B packets) and occupying a total area of 18.5 mm² (22 nm FDSOI).

Index Terms—in-network compute, packet processing, specialized architecture, sPIN.

I. MOTIVATION

Today’s cloud and high-performance datacenters form a crucial pillar of compute infrastructures and are growing at unprecedented speeds. At the core, they are a collection of machines connected by a fast network carrying petabits per second of internal and external traffic. Emerging online services such as video communication, streaming, and on-line collaboration increase the incoming and outgoing traffic volume. Furthermore, the growing deployment of specialized accelerators and general trends towards disaggregation exacerbates the quickly growing network load. Packet processing capabilities are a top performance target for datacenters.

These requirements have led to a wave of modernization in datacenter networks: not only are high-bandwidth technologies going up to 200 Gbit/s gaining wide adoption but endpoints must also be tuned to reduce packet processing overheads. Specifically, remote direct memory access (RDMA) networks move much of the packet and protocol processing to fixed-function hardware units in the network card and directly access

data into user-space memory. Even though this greatly reduces packet processing overheads on the CPU, the incoming data must still be processed. A flurry of specialized technologies exists to move additional parts of this processing into network cards, e.g., FPGAs virtualization support [22], P4 simple rewriting rules [13], or triggered operations [9].

Streaming processing in the network (sPIN) [28] defines a unified programming model and architecture for network acceleration beyond simple RDMA. It provides a user-level interface, similar to CUDA for compute acceleration, considering the specialties and constraints of low-latency line-rate packet processing. It defines a flexible and programmable network instruction set architecture (NISA) that not only lowers the barrier of entry but also supports a large set of use-cases [28]. For example, Di Girolamo et al. demonstrate up to 10x speedups for serialization and deserialization (marshalling) of non-consecutive data [20].

While the NISA defined by sPIN can be implemented on existing SmartNICs [1], their microarchitecture (often standard ARM SoCs) is not optimized for packet-processing tasks. In this work, we define an open-source high-performance and low-power microarchitecture for sPIN network interface cards (NICs). We break first ground by developing principles for NIC microarchitectures that enable flexible packet processing at 400 Gbit/s line-rate.

As core contributions in this work, we

- establish principles for flexible and programmable NIC-based packet processing microarchitectures,
- design and implement a fully-functional 32-core SoC for packet processing that can be added into any NIC pipeline,
- analyze latencies, message rates, and bandwidths for a large set of example processing handlers, and
- open-source the SoC design to benefit the community.

We implement PsPIN in synthesizable hardware description language (HDL) code. Overall, it occupies less than 20mm² in a 22nm FDSOI process, which is about 25x smaller than an Intel Skylake Xeon die. We show how, given the nature of in-network compute tasks, a PsPIN unit can achieve similar or higher throughput than more complex architectures, like Xeon- or ARM- based ones by using at most 6.3W.

Solution	L	P	G	U	Notes
Azure AccellNet [22]	👍	👎	👍	👎	FPGA-based NICs; Flow-steering.
P4 [13]*, FlexNIC [32]	👍	👍	👍	👎	Packet steering and rewriting. FlexNIC adds memory support. *Runs on NICs and switches.
Mellanox SHARP [24]	👍	👎	👍	👍	Data aggregation and reduction. Runs on switches.
Portals 4 [9], INCA [49]	👍	👍	👎	👍	Sequences of predefined actions can be expressed with triggered operations. Both target NICs.
Mellanox CORE-Direct [25]	👍	👍	👎	👍	Sequence of predefined actions can be chained. Targets switches.
Cray Aries Reduction Engine [6]	👍	👎	👍	👍	Data reductions (up to 64 bytes). Runs on switches.
Quadrics [43], Myrinet [16]	👍	👍	👍	👎	Users define threads to run on the NIC / NIC is re-programmable by users.
SmartNICs [2], [1]	👍	👍	👍	👎	Runs full linux stack on the NIC; Offloading of new code requires flashing.
FPGA packet parsing pipeline [8]	👍	👍	👍	👎	Only packet parsing, read-only packets, might require FPGA reconfiguration. Target NICs.
eBPF (host) [39]	👎	👍	👍	👎	Runs user-defined code (eBPF code) in virtual machine in the OS kernel.
eBPF (Neronome) [33], hXDP [15]	👍	👍	👍	👎	eBPF programs can be offloaded to NIC.
DPDK [46]	👎	👍	👍	👎	Runs in user space. Applications can poll for new raw packets from the NIC.
StRoM [51]	👍	👍	👍	👎	Handlers for DMA streams are implemented on FPGA NIC.
NICA [21]	👍	👍	👎	👎	Bind kernels running on on-NIC accelerators to user sockets.
PANIC [36]	👍	👍	👍	👎	Applications compose execution of pre-installed compute units. Targets NICs.
sPIN [28]	👍	👍	👍	👍	Applications define C/C++ packet handlers to map to different messages/flows. Targets NICs.

TABLE I

L: LOCATION (👍 ON NICs OR SWITCHES; 👍 ON NICs BUT OUTSIDE THE PACKET PIPELINE; 👎 ON HOST CPU). P: PROGRAMMABILITY (👍 FULLY PROGRAMMABLE; 👍 LIMITED PROGRAMMABILITY; 👎 PREDEFINED FUNCTIONS). G: GRANULARITY (👍 MESSAGE AND PACKETS; 👍 ONLY PACKETS; 👎 ONLY MESSAGES). U: USABILITY (👍 USABLE BY APPLICATIONS AND PRIVILEGED USERS; 👎 ONLY BY PRIVILEGED USERS).

II. IN-NETWORK COMPUTE

In-network compute is the capability of an interconnection network to process, steer, and produce data according to a set of programmable actions. The exact definition of *action* depends on the specific in-network-compute solution: it can vary from pre-defined actions (e.g., pass or drop a packet according to a set of rules) to fully programmable packet or message handlers (e.g., sPIN handlers).

There are several advantages of computing in the network:

- (1) *More overlap*. Applications can define actions to execute on incoming data. Letting the network execute them allows applications to overlap these tasks with other useful work;
- (2) *Lower latency*. The network can promptly react to incoming data (cf. Portals 4 triggered operations [9], virtual functions [22], sPIN handlers), immediately executing actions depending on it. Doing the same on the host requires applications to poll for new data, check for dependent actions, and then execute them.
- (3) *Higher throughput*. Some in-network-compute solutions enable stream processing of the incoming data. For example, sPIN can run packet handlers on each incoming packet, potentially improving the overall throughput.
- (4) *Less resource contention*. Running tasks in the network can reduce the volume of data moved through the PCIe bus and the memory hierarchy. This implies fewer data movements, less memory contention and cache pollution, potentially improving the performance of host CPU tasks.

Table I surveys existing in-network-compute solutions. This classification focuses on the high-level characteristics of these solutions, comparing them by the location where policies are run, the level of programmability, the granularity at which the actions are applied, and their usability.

(L) Location. Policies can be executed at different points along the path from the endpoint sending the data to the endpoint receiving it. We classify in-network-compute solutions as: 👍 running in network devices (e.g., on NICs or switches); 👍 running in network devices but not on the packet pipeline (e.g., SmartNICs act as close-to-network endpoints, running full Linux stack); 👎 if they run on the host CPUs.

(P) Programmability. It defines the expressiveness of the actions. Network solutions enabling fully programmable actions that can access the message/packet header and payload, access the NIC and host memory, and issue new network operations (e.g., RDMA put or gets) are marked with 👍. Solutions that provide a predefined set of actions that can be composed among themselves (e.g., P4 match-actions or Portals 4 triggered operations) are marked with 👍. Solutions providing only predefined functions are marked with 👎.

(G) Granularity. Actions can be applied to full messages (👎), requiring to first fully receive the message, or to single packets, as they are received (👍). Solutions enabling both types of actions are marked with 👍.

(U) Usability. It defines which entities can install actions into the network. In-network-compute solutions enabling user applications and libraries (even in multi-tenant settings) to install actions are marked with 👍. Solutions that require elevated privileges, service disruption, and/or device memory flashing to install new actions are marked with 👎.

Among the solutions of Table I, sPIN is the only one letting user-space applications define per-message or per-packet tasks (called handlers) that are executed in the NIC. sPIN handlers can access and modify packet data, share NIC memory, and issue NIC and DMA commands. Handlers can be installed on the NIC without disrupting operations and memory isolation must be guaranteed (see Section III-B2). For these reasons, we focus on the sPIN programming model, investigate the challenges of building a sPIN engine, and introduce PsPIN, a general and open-source sPIN implementation. By open-sourcing the hardware design of PsPIN under a permissive open-source license (Solderpad), we want to encourage its usage and foster the creation of prototypes by anyone in the community.

A. sPIN: Streaming processing in the network

The key idea of sPIN is to extend RDMA by enabling users to define simple processing tasks, called *handlers*, to be executed directly on the NIC. A message sent through the

Fig. 1. sPIN abstract machine model.

network is seen as a sequence of packets: the first packet is defined as *header*, the last one as *completion*, and all the intermediate ones as *payload*. As the packets of a message reach their destination, the receiving NIC invokes the respective packet handlers. For each message, three types of handlers are defined: the *header handler*, executed only on the header packet; the *payload handler*, executed on all the packets, and the *completion handler*, executed after all packets have been processed. Handlers are defined by applications running on the host and cross-compiled for the NIC microarchitecture. The programming model that sPIN proposes is similar to CUDA [40] and OpenCL [52]: the difference is that in these frameworks, applications define kernels to be offloaded to GPUs. In sPIN, the kernels (i.e., handlers) are offloaded to the NIC, and their execution is triggered by the arrival of packets. Figure 1 sketches the sPIN abstract machine model.

Host applications define packet handlers and associate them with message descriptors. Packet handlers are optional: e.g., by specifying either the header or completion handler and no payload handler, only one packet handler for the full message will be executed. Message descriptors, together with packet handlers, are installed into the NIC. Incoming packets are matched to message descriptors and handlers are executed on Handler Processing Units (HPUs). Handlers can also issue NIC commands and DMA transfers to/from the host memory.

1) *Architectural Specialties*: The sPIN abstract machine model specifies a streaming execution model with microarchitectural requirements that are quite different from classical specialized packet processing engines, which normally constraint the type of actions that can be performed or the entity that can program them, and traditional compute cores. We now outline a set of architectural properties that a sPIN implementation should provide to enable fully-programmable high-performance packet processing.

S1. Highly parallel. Many payload packets can be processed in parallel. The higher the number of HPUs, the longer the handlers can run without becoming a bottleneck.

S2. Fast scheduling. Arriving packets must be scheduled to HPU cores while maintaining ordering requirements that mandate that header handlers execute before payload handlers that execute before completion handlers.

S3. Fast explicit memory access. Packet processing has low temporal locality by definition (a packet is seen only once), hence scratchpad memories are better than caches.

S4. Local handler state. Handlers can keep state across packets of a message as well as multiple messages. If the memory is partitioned, then scheduling needs to ensure that the state is reachable/addressable.

S5. Low latency, full throughput. To minimize the time a packet stays in the NIC, the time from when the packet is seen by sPIN to when the handlers execute should be minimized. Furthermore, the sPIN unit must not obstruct line-rate.

S6. Area and power efficiency. To lead to an easier integration of a sPIN unit in a broader range of NIC architectures.

S7. Handler isolation. Handlers processing a message should not be able to access memory belonging to other messages, especially if they belong to different applications.

S8. Configurability. A sPIN unit should be easily re-configurable to be scaled to different network requirements.

III. PsPIN

PsPIN is a sPIN implementation designed to match the architecture specialties of Section II-A1. PsPIN builds on top of the PULP (parallel ultra-low power) platform [48], a silicon-proven [23] and open [55] architectural template for scalable and energy-efficient processing. PULP implements the RISC-V ISA [59] and organizes the processing elements in clusters: each cluster has a fixed number of cores (32-bit, single-issue, in-order) and single-cycle-accessible scratchpad memory (**S3**). The system can be scaled by adding or removing clusters (**S1**). *We have implemented all hardware components of PsPIN in synthesizable hardware description language (HDL) code.*

A. Architecture Overview

PsPIN has a modular architecture, where the HPUs are grouped into processing clusters. The HPUs are implemented as RISC-V cores, and each cluster is equipped with a single-cycle access scratchpad memory called L1 memory. All clusters are interconnected to each other (i.e., HPUs can access data in remote L1s) and to three off-cluster memories (L2): the packet buffer, the handler memory, and the program memory. Figure 2 shows an overview of how PsPIN integrates in a generic NIC model and its architecture. We adopt a generic NIC model to identify the general building blocks of a NIC architecture. Later, in Section III-D, we discuss how PsPIN can be integrated in existing NIC architectures.

Fig. 2. NIC model and PsPIN architecture overview.

Host applications access program and handler memories to offload handlers code and data, respectively. The management of these memory regions is left to the NIC driver, which is in charge of exposing an interface to the applications in order to move code and data. The toolchain and the NIC driver extensions to offload handlers code and data are out of the scope of this work. Once both code and data for the handlers are offloaded, the host builds an execution context,

which contains: pointers to the handler functions (header, payload, and completion handlers), a pointer to the allocated handler memory, and information on how to match packets that need to be processed according to this execution context. The execution context is offloaded to the NIC and it is used by the NIC inbound engine to forward packets to PsPIN.

Receiving data. Data is received by the NIC inbound engine, which is normally interfaced with the host for copying it to host memory. In a PsPIN-NIC, the inbound engine is also interfaced to the PsPIN unit. The inbound engine must be able to distinguish packets that need to be processed by PsPIN from the ones taking the classical non-processing path. To make this distinction, it matches packets to PsPIN execution contexts and, if a match is found, it forwards the packet to the PsPIN unit. Otherwise, the packet is copied to the host as normal. While some networks already have the concept of packet matching (e.g., RDMA NICs match packets to queue pairs), in others this concept is missing and needs to be introduced to enable packet-level processing (see Section III-D).

Packets to be processed on the NIC are copied to the L2 packet buffer. Once the copy is complete, the NIC inbound engine sends a Handler Execution Request (HER) to PsPIN’s packet scheduler. The HER contains all information necessary to schedule a handler to process the packet, which are a pointer to the packet in the L2 packet buffer and an execution context. If the packet buffer is full, the NIC inbound engine can either back pressure the senders [30], send explicit congestion notifications [47], drop packets, or kill connections [9]. The exact policy to adopt depends on the network in which PsPIN is integrated and the choice is similar to the case where the host cannot consume incoming packets fast enough.

The packet scheduler selects the processing cluster that processes the new packet. The cluster-local scheduler (CSCHED) is in charge of starting a DMA copy of the packets from the L2 packet buffer to the L1 Tightly-Coupled Data Memory (TCDM) and selecting an idle HPU (H) where to run handlers for packets that are available in L1. Once the packet processing completes, a notification is sent back to the NIC to let it update its view of the packet buffer (e.g., move the head pointer in case the packet buffer is managed as a ring buffer).

Sending Data. Packet handlers, in addition to processing the packet data, can send data over the network or move data to/from host memory. To send data directly from the NIC, the sPIN API provides an RDMA-*put* operation: When a handler issues this operation, the PsPIN runtime translates it into a NIC command, which is sent to the NIC outbound engine. If the NIC outbound engine cannot receive new commands, the handler blocks waiting for it to become available again. The NIC outbound can send data from either the L2 packet memory, the L2 handler memory, or L1 memories, or it can specify a host memory address as data source, behaving as a host-issued command. To move data to/from the host, the handlers can issue DMA operations: These operations translate to commands that are forwarded to the off-cluster DMA engine, which writes data to host memory through PCIe.

Fig. 3. PsPIN control path overview.

B. Control path

Figure 3 shows the PsPIN control path, which includes: ① receiving HERs from the NIC inbound engine, ② scheduling packets, handling commands from the handlers, and ⑦ sending completion notifications back to the NIC.

1) *Inter-cluster packet scheduling:* PsPIN is informed of new packets to process by receiving HERs from the NIC inbound engine ①. The HER is received by the packet scheduler, which is composed of the Message Processing Queue (MPQ) engine and the task dispatcher. The MPQ engine handles scheduling dependencies between packets. These dependencies are defined by the sPIN programming model:

- the header handler is executed on the first packet of a message and no payload handler can start before its completion;
- the completion handler is executed after the last packet of a message is received and all payload handlers are completed.

A *message* is a sequence of packets mapped to an MPQ and matched to an execution context. We let the NIC define the packets that are part of a message or flow. Once the last packet of a message arrives, the NIC marks the corresponding HER with an end-of-message flag, letting PsPIN run the completion handler when all other handlers of that MPQ complete.

Task dispatcher. The task dispatcher selects the processing cluster where to forward a task for its execution ③. We introduce a dedicated hardware unit for dispatching packets to clusters. A software solution would not provide enough bandwidth to schedule packets at line rate. If we consider a target bandwidth of 400 Gbit/s and 64 B packets, we get one packet every 1.28 ns, which requires to schedule a packet every 1.28 cycles on average. A cluster can accept new tasks when it has enough space in its L1 to store the packet data. We use the message ID, which is included in the HER, to determine the *home cluster* of a message: the task dispatcher tries to schedule packets to their home clusters. If the home cluster cannot accept it, then the least loaded cluster is selected. The task dispatcher blocks if there are no available clusters.

Fig. 4. Data copy latency and bandwidth.

The rationale behind the concept of home cluster is given by the fact that handlers processing packets of the same message

can share L1 memory, hence scheduling them on the same cluster avoids remote L1 accesses. Figure 4 shows the memory latency and bandwidth experienced by a single core when copying data from local or remote memories using different access types (i.e., load/stores, DMA). As each core can execute one single-word memory access at a time, the latency for accessing a chunk of data increases linearly with its size. The DMA engine, on the other hand, moves data in bursts, so multiple words can be “in-flight” concurrently.

Handler execution and completion notification. Within a processing cluster, task execution requests are handled by the cluster-local scheduler. We describe the details of intra-cluster handler scheduling in Section III-B2. During their execution, handlers can issue commands that are handled by a command unit 4. We define three types of commands to interact with the NIC outbound and with the off-cluster DMA engine:

- NIC commands to send data over the network: a handler can forward the packet or generate new ones.
- DMA commands to move data to/from host memory. The host virtual addresses can be stored in application-defined data structures in handler memory.
- HostDirect commands are similar to DMA commands but, instead of a source address, they carry 32 B immediate data that is written directly to the host memory address.

Command responses 5 are used to inform the handlers of the completion of the issued commands or error conditions.

Once a handler terminates and there are no in-flight commands for which a response is still pending, a completion notification is generated 6. The MPQ engine uses this notification to track the state of message queues (e.g., mark a queue as ready when the header handler completes). The notification is also forwarded to the NIC inbound engine, which uses it to free sections in the L2 packet buffer.

Fig. 5. PsPIN processing cluster.

2) *Intra-cluster handler scheduling:* Tasks are received by the cluster-local scheduler (CSCHEDED) that is in charge of scheduling them on the HPUs. For each new task, it starts a DMA transfer of the packet data from L2 to L1. Moving the packet data to L1 enables single-cycle access from the cores. Once a transfer completes, the corresponding task is popped from the queue and scheduled to an idle HPU. At 400 Gbit/s, a cluster receives tasks for 64 B packets every 5.12 ns on average ($1.28 \text{ ns} \cdot 4$). This time budget is not sufficient to handle intra-cluster scheduling in software. For comparison, issuing a DMA command already takes 6 cycles. Furthermore, having the scheduling algorithm running on the HPUs, e.g., in a cooperative scheduling approach, would require to run it in a higher privilege mode in order to guarantee handlers

isolation, adding additional overheads. Hence, we opted for a hardware intra-cluster scheduler, which also allowed us to have a lighter runtime running on the HPUs. HPUs are interfaced with a memory-mapped device, the HPU driver, from which they can read information about the task to execute.

The PsPIN runtime running on the HPU consists of a loop executing the following steps: (1) Read the handler function pointer from the HPU driver. If the HPU driver has no task/handler to execute, it stops the HPUs by clock-gating it. When a task arrives, the HPU is enabled and the load completes. (2) Prepare the handler arguments (e.g., packet memory pointer). (3) Call the handler function. (4) Write to a doorbell memory location in the HPU driver to inform it that the handler execution is completed. The HPU driver sends a completion notification as soon as it detects that there are no in-flight commands issued by the completed task. The HPU driver can buffer a completed task for which the completion notification cannot be sent and start processing a new one.

Since multiple HPU drivers can send feedback and issue commands at the same time, we use round-robin arbiters to select, at every cycle, an HPU that can send a feedback and one that can issue a command. Figure 5 shows an overview of a PsPIN processing cluster. The figure shows only the connections relevant to the scheduling processes and to the handling of handler commands. In reality, the HPUs are also interfaced to the cluster DMA engine and can issue arbitrary DMA transfers from/to the accessible L2 handler memory.

Memory accesses and protection. Handlers processing packets matched to the same execution context share the L2 handler memory region that has been allocated by the application when defining the execution context. Additionally, each message shares a statically allocated scratchpad area in the L1 of the home cluster. In particular, L1 memories, which are 1 MiB each in our configuration, contain: the packet buffer (32 KiB), the runtime data structure (e.g., HPU stacks, 8 KiB), the message scratchpads (984 KiB). Scratchpads are allocated through the NIC driver and associated with execution contexts.

To protect against illegal memory accesses and guarantee handler isolation (S7), the HPU driver configures the RISC-V Physical Memory Protection (PMP) unit [58] for each task, allowing the core to access only a subset of the address space (e.g., handler code, packet memory, L1 scratchpad). The handlers are always run in user mode. In case of a memory access violation or any other exception, an interrupt is generated and handled by the PsPIN runtime. The exception handling consists of resetting the environment (e.g., stack pointer) for the next handler execution and informing the HPU driver of the error condition. The HPU driver will then send a command to the HostDirect unit to write the error condition to the execution context descriptor in host memory. A failed handler leads to the release of the occupied resources.

3) *Monitoring and control:* While processing packets on the NIC, there are two scenarios that must be prevented to ensure correct operation: (1) Packets of a message stop coming and the end-of-message is not received. This can be due to

Fig. 6. Relation between handlers execution times and line rate.

factors such as network failure, network congestion, or bugs in applications or protocols. (2) Slow handlers that cannot process packets at line rate. To detect case (1), we use a pseudo-LRU [27] solution on active MPQs (i.e., MPQs which are receiving packets). Every time an MPQ is accessed (i.e., packet pushed to it), it is moved to the back of the LRU list. If the candidate victim does not receive packets for more than a threshold specified in the execution context of the message that activated it, the MPQ is reset. This event is signaled to the host through the execution context descriptor. Case (2) is detected by the HPU drivers themselves by using a watchdog timer that generates an interrupt on the HPU and causes the runtime to reset it. The timer is configured according to a threshold specified in the execution context either by the NIC driver or the application itself. This case is handled similarly to memory access violations by notifying the host of the error condition through the execution context descriptor.

To understand the time budget available to the handlers, Figure 6 shows the relation between handlers execution time and line rate. We assume a PsPIN configuration with 32 HPUs. On the left, it shows the maximum duration handlers should have to process packets at line rate for different packet sizes, in case of 200 Gbit/s and 400 Gbit/s networks. On the right, it shows how the processing throughput is affected by handlers duration for different packet sizes and network speeds.

C. Data path

We now discuss how data flows within PsPIN, explaining the design choices made to guarantee optimal bandwidth. We equip PsPIN with three interconnects: the NIC-Host interconnect, which interfaces the NIC and the host to PsPIN memories; the DMA interconnect, which interfaces the cluster-local DMA engines to both L2 packet buffer and handler memories; and the processing-elements (PE) interconnect, which allows HPUs to read from either L2 memories or remote L1s. Both NIC-Host and DMA interconnect have wide data ports (512 bit), while the PE interconnect is designed for finer granularity accesses (32 bit). Since PsPIN is clocked at 1 GHz, the offered bandwidth of these interconnects is 512 Gbit/s and 32 Gbit/s, respectively. PsPIN’s on-chip interconnects, memory controllers, and DMA engine are based on [35].

Figure 7 shows an overview of the PsPIN memories, interconnects, and units that can move data (in gray if they are interfaced to but not within PsPIN). We identify three critical data flows that require full bandwidth in order to not obstruct line rate and optimize PsPIN data paths to achieve this goal.

- *Flow 1: from NIC inbound to L2 packet buffer to clusters’ L1s.* The NIC inbound writes packets to the L2 packet buffer at line rate and, in the worst case, this data is always copied to the L1s of the processing clusters by their DMA

Fig. 7. PsPIN data path overview. Bold arrows represent AXI4 connections with 512 bit data width. Thin arrows represent 32 bit AXI4 connections. Arrow heads indicate AXI4 “slave” ports, while tails are for “master” ports.

engines, before starting the handlers. The main bottleneck of this data flow can be the L2 packet buffer, which is accessed in both write and read directions.

- *Flow 2: from L2/L1 to host memory.* Assuming all handlers copy the data to host, we have a steady flow of data towards the host memory. The data source is specified in the command issued by the handlers and can be either the L2 packet buffer, the L2 handler memory, or the clusters’ L1s. This data is moved by the off-cluster DMA engine, which interfaces to an IOMMU to translate the virtual addresses specified in the handler command to physical ones. The IOMMU is updated by the NIC driver when the host registers memory that can be accessed by the NIC.
- *Flow 3: from L2/L1 to NIC outboard.* Similar to flow 2, but the data is moved towards the NIC outboard engine. We assume the NIC outboard has its own DMA engine, which it uses to read data.

All the identified critical flows can involve the L2 packet buffer. To avoid being a bottleneck, this memory must provide full bandwidth to the NIC inbound engine and to the cluster-local DMA engines (flow 1), plus it must provide full bandwidth to the system composed of the NIC outboard engine and the off-cluster DMA (flow 2 + flow 3), letting them reach up to 256 Gbit/s read-bandwidth each under full load. To achieve this goal, we implement the L2 packet buffer as 4 MiB, two-ports full-duplex, multi-banked (32 banks) word-interleaved memory. With 512 bit words, the L2 packet buffer is suitable more for wide accesses than single (32 bit) load/store accesses from HPUs. In fact, if handlers are going to frequently access packets, then their execution context can be configured to let PsPIN move packets to L1, before the handlers start. The maximum bandwidth that the L2 packet buffer can sustain is 512 Gbit/s per port, full duplex. This bandwidth can be achieved in case there are no bank conflicts. One port of the L2 packet buffer is accessible through the NIC-Host interconnect, where the NIC inbound engine is connected. Only the NIC inbound engine can write through this port, hence it gets the full write bandwidth. Other units connected to the NIC-Host interconnect that can access the L2 packet buffer, namely the NIC outboard engine and the off-cluster DMA engine, share the read bandwidth. The second port is connected to both DMA and PE interconnects. This configuration allows supporting a maximum line rate of 512 Gbit/s, making PsPIN suitable for up to 400 Gbit/s networks.

L2 handler and program memory. The L2 handler memory is less bandwidth-critical than the L2 packet buffer, but not less important. In the current configuration, the handler memory is 4 MiB. The sPIN programming model allows the host to access memory regions on the NIC to, e.g., write data needed by the handlers or read data back when a message is fully processed. Host applications can allocate memory regions in this memory through the NIC driver, which manages the allocation state. The host can copy data in the handler memory before packets triggering handlers using it start arriving. For example, Di Girolamo et al. [20] use this memory to store information about MPI datatypes, deploying general handlers that process the packets according to the memory layout described in the handler memory. Differently from the packet buffer, we foresee that the handler memory can be targeted more frequently by the HPUs with 32-bit word accesses, hence we adopt 64 bit-wide banks to reduce the probability of bank conflicts. Similarly, to the L2 packet buffer, the handler memory can be involved by flows 2 and 3 and offers a maximum bandwidth of 512 Gbit/s per port, full duplex.

The program memory (32 KiB) stores handlers code. It is accessed by the host to offload code and by the PE interconnect to refill the per-cluster 4 KiB instruction cache. Since this memory is not on the critical path, we implement it as single-port, half-duplex, with 64 Gbit/s bandwidth. The per-cluster instruction cache is 4-way set associative with 8 ports. The concept of the home cluster, which tries to schedule packets of the same message (i.e., same handlers' code) to the same cluster, helps to reduce instruction cache pollution.

D. NIC integration

We described PsPIN within the context of the NIC model discussed in Section III-A but, *how to integrate a PsPIN unit in existing networks?* To answer this question, we identify a set of NIC *capabilities*, some of which are required for integrating PsPIN, and others that are optional but can provide a richer handler semantic. The required capabilities are:

Message/flow matching. Packet handlers are defined per message/flow on the receiver side. The NIC must match a packet to a message/flow to identify the handler(s) to execute. We do not explicitly define messages or flows because this depends on the network where PsPIN is integrated into. For PsPIN, a message or flow is a sequence of packets targeting the same message processing queue (MPQ, see Section III-B3). The feedback channel to the NIC inbound engine is used to communicate when an MPQ becomes idle and can be remapped to a new NIC-defined message or flow.

Header first. The first packet that is processed by PsPIN must carry the information characterizing the message. This requirement can be relaxed if packets carry information to identify a message or flow (e.g., TCP, UDP).

NICs can provide additional capabilities that can (1) extend the functionalities that the handlers have access to and (2) let the applications make stronger assumptions on the network behavior. Applications can query the NIC capabilities, potentially providing different handlers depending on the available

capabilities. One such capability is *reliability*. With a reliable network layer, PsPIN is guaranteed to receive all packets of a message and to not receive duplicated packets. With this capability, applications can employ non-idempotent handlers. Otherwise, the handlers have to take into account that, e.g., they can be executed more than once on the same packet.

1) *Match-action tables:* NICs providing match-action table abstraction [44], [32], [13] are an ideal candidate for a PsPIN integration. With this abstraction, users can install packet parsing rules that lead to specific actions. To integrate PsPIN, a new action should be made available that has the effect of forwarding the matched packet to the PsPIN unit, together with an execution context that is associated with the match-action entry. This solution enables applications to define their own concept of message or flow, providing the greatest flexibility. For example, applications can define a flow as a TCP stream (i.e., by matching on both IP and TCP headers) or as all UDP packets targeting a specific port. This solution would not be affected by ossification because the way flows are defined can be programmed. For example, applications using HTTP/2 [12] that multiplex multiple streams within the same long-lived TCP connection can define a PsPIN message/flow as a single stream (i.e., matching on the HTTP/2 header). Similarly, transport protocols like QUIC [31] can match PsPIN messages/flows on single streams of long-lived connections.

2) *RDMA-Capable Networks:* Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA) networks let applications expose memory regions over the network, enabling remote processes to access them for reading or writing data. When using RDMA, applications register memory regions on the NIC, so that its IOMMU can translate virtual to physical addresses. Whenever a remote process wants to, e.g., perform a write operation, it has to specify where in the target memory the data has to be written. This memory location can be directly specified by its target virtual memory address in the write request [30], [6], or indirectly [9]. In the indirect case, the application not only registers the memory but also specifies a receive descriptor that can be matched by incoming remote memory access requests: e.g., in Portals 4, these descriptors are named list entries or matched list entries according to whether they are associated with a set of matching bits or not.

In general, RDMA NICs already perform the packet matching on the NIC. In the direct case, the NIC matches the virtual address carried by the request to a physical address. In the indirect case, the NIC matches the packet to the receive descriptor, to derive the target memory location. Hence, the required *message matching* capability is provided; the question is: to which object do we attach the PsPIN handlers? Table II reports different RDMA-capable networks and objects where the PsPIN handlers can be attached. For example, associating handlers to the InfiniBand queue pair means that all packets targeting that queue pair will be processed by PsPIN.

The second required capability is *header first*. For InfiniBand, this is given by the in-order delivery that the network already provides. For other networks that cannot guarantee that, the NIC must be able to buffer or discard payloads

Network	Interface	Handlers Descriptor
InfiniBand [30], RoCE [53]	ibverbs [11]	Queue Pair
Bull BXI [19], Cray Slingshot [50]	Portals 4[9]	Match List Entry
Cray Gemini [7], Cray Aries [6]	uGNI, DMAPP [5]	Memory Handle

TABLE II

RDMA NETWORKS AND SPIN HANDLERS ATTACH POINTS.

packets arriving before the header packet. RDMA-capable networks already implement reliability at the network layer, hence applications can adopt non-idempotent handlers.

E. NIC driver

To expose packet-processing functionalities, the NIC driver needs to implement the sPIN interface described by Hoefler et al. [28]. In particular, the driver manages the NIC memory by letting applications allocate memory regions for data (e.g., handler memory) and code (e.g., program memory). The PsPIN unit is not involved in applications memory management, which is delegated to the software layer. A detailed description of a NIC driver is out of the scope of this work.

F. Special cases and exceptions

Can PsPIN deadlock if no processing cluster can accept new tasks? In this case, the task dispatcher will block, waiting for a queue to become available again and this will create back-pressure towards the NIC inbound engine. The system cannot deadlock because the processing clusters can keep running since they are not dependent on new HERs to arrive. The header-before-payloads dependency does not cause problems because if payload handlers are waiting for the header, then it is guaranteed that the header is being already processed (because of the *header-first* requisite and the in-order scheduling guaranteed by the MPQ engine on a per-message basis). If badly-written handlers deadlock, the HPU driver watchdog will trigger causing the handler termination.

What if a message is not fully delivered? The completion feedback will not be triggered causing resources (e.g., message state in the MPQ engine) to not be freed. PsPIN can detect this case and force resource release (see Section III-B3).

How is encrypted traffic handled? Handlers are responsible for the decryption of incoming data. We foresee the possibility of supporting user handlers with libraries providing common functions like crypto primitives. Given the modular design of PsPIN, a per-cluster crypto engine can be deployed to enable hardware-accelerated crypto primitives (e.g., AES-EBC). While a crypto engine for PULP (hence PsPIN-compatible) already exist [26], we consider its evaluation as future work.

IV. EVALUATION

Our evaluation aims to answer the following questions: (1) How big is PsPIN in terms of post-synthesis area and how does that scale with the number of HPUs? (2) In which cases can PsPIN sustain line rate? (3) Does the choice of implementing sPIN on top of a RISC-V based architecture with a flat non-coherent memory hierarchy pay off? What are the trade-offs of choosing more complex architectures for sPIN?

Simulation environment. We simulate PsPIN in a **cycle-accurate testbench comprised of SystemVerilog modules.**

We use synthesizable modules for all PsPIN components. We develop simulation-only modules modeling the NIC inbound and outbound engines. Our inbound engine takes a trace of packets as input and injects them in PsPIN at a given rate. The outbound engine reads data from PsPIN according to the received commands, generating memory pressure. The host interface is emulated with a PCIe model (PCIe 5.0, 16 lanes), implemented as a fixed-rate data sink. Unless otherwise specified, we do not limit the packet generator injection rate in order to test the maximum throughput PsPIN can offer. Packet handlers are compiled with the PULP SDK, which contains an extended version of GCC 7.1.1 (riscv32). All handlers are compiled with full optimizations on `(-O3 -flto)`.

A. Hardware Synthesis and Power

We synthesized PsPIN in GlobalFoundries' 22 nm fully depleted silicon on insulator (FDSOI) technology using Synopsys DesignCompiler 2019.12, and we were able to close the timing of the system at 1 GHz. We employ Invecas' memory compiler to generate SRAM macros that are tailored to the architectural requirements. Area and power measurements are summarized in Table III. Including memories, the entire accelerator has a complexity on the order of 95 MGE.¹ Of the overall area, the four clusters (including their L1 memory and the intra-cluster scheduler) occupy 43%, the L2 memory 51%, the inter-cluster scheduler 3%, and the inter-cluster interconnect and L2 memory controllers another 3%. The L2 memory macros occupy a total area of 9.48 mm². Depending on the NIC architecture where PsPIN is integrated into, the L2 packet buffer could be mapped to the NIC packet buffer, saving memory area. The area of the clusters is dominated by the L1 memory macros, which take 1.65 mm² per cluster. The instruction cache and the cluster interconnect have a complexity of ca. 700 kGE per cluster, which corresponds to ca. 0.2 mm² at 70% placement density. Each core has a complexity of ca. 50 kGE, which corresponds to ca. 0.014 mm². The total cluster area is ca. 1.99 mm². The total area of our architecture is ca. 18.5 mm² (**S6**). For comparison, from [37], [45] it can be inferred that a Mellanox BlueField SoC, scaled to 16 ARM A72 cores (22 nm), would occupy ca. 51 mm².

Component	Area (mm ²)			Power (W)		
	Unit	Total	Perc.	Unit	Total	Perc.
PsPIN	18.47	18.47	100.0%	6.08	6.08	100.0%
↳ L2 memories (×1)	9.48	9.48	51.3%	1.09	1.10	18.1%
↳ Interconnect (×1)	0.57	0.57	3.0%	0.71	0.71	11.7%
↳ Cluster (×4)	1.99	7.95	43.0%	0.94	3.77	62.0%
↳ LI (×1)	1.65	1.65	82.9%	0.52	0.52	55.3%
↳ Core (×8)	0.01	0.08	4.0%	0.02	0.14	15.3%
↳ Instr. cache (×1)	0.08	0.08	4.0%	0.14	0.14	15.1%
↳ Interconnect (×1)	0.06	0.06	3.0%	0.11	0.11	11.3%

TABLE III

AREA AND ENERGY OF MAIN PsPIN COMPONENTS. PERCENTAGES ARE RELATIVE TO THE PARENT COMPONENT.

We derive a worst-case upper bound for the power consumption of our architecture by assuming 100% toggle rate on all logic cells and 50/50% read/write activity at each memory macro. The overall power envelope is 6.1 W, 99.8%

¹One gate equivalent (GE) equals 0.199 μm² in GF 22 nm FDSOI.

of which is dynamic power (S6). The four clusters consume 62% of the total power, ca. 3.8 W. Within each cluster, the L1 memory consumes ca. 55% of the power. The L2 memory consumes 18% of the total power, ca. 1.1 W. The inter-cluster scheduler consumes 8% of the total power, ca. 0.5 W. The inter-cluster interconnect and L2 memory controllers consume 11.7%, ca. 0.7 W. As our architecture offers 32 HPUs, the power normalized to the number of HPUs is 190 mW.

B. Microbenchmarks

We now investigate the performance characteristics of PsPIN: we first discuss the latencies experienced by a packet when being processed by PsPIN. Then, we study the maximum packet processing throughput that PsPIN can achieve and how the complexity of the packet handlers can affect it.

1) *Packet Latency*: We define the packet latency as the time that elapses from when PsPIN receives an HER from the NIC inbound engine to when the completion notification for that packet is sent back to it. It does not include the time needed by the NIC inbound engine to write the packet to the L2 packet buffer. The measurements of this section are taken in an unloaded system by instrumenting the cycle-accurate simulation. Overall, we observe latencies ranging from 26 ns for 64 B packets to 40 ns for 1024 B ones. In particular, a task execution request takes 3 ns to arrive to the cluster-local scheduler (i.e., CSCHED in Figure 5). At that point, the packet is copied to the cluster L1 by the cluster-local DMA engine. This transfer has latencies varying from 12 ns for 64 B packets to 26 ns for 1024 B packets. Once the data reaches L1, the task is assigned to an HPU driver in a single cycle. The HPU runtime takes 7 ns to invoke the handler: this time is used for reading the handler function pointer, setting up the handler’s arguments, and making the jump. Once the handler completes, the runtime makes a single-cycle store to the HPU driver to inform it of the completion. The completion notification takes 1 ns to get back to the NIC inbound engine, but it can be delayed of additional 6 ns and 2 ns in case of the round-robin arbiters prioritize other HPUs and clusters, respectively.

2) *Packet processing throughput*: In Section III-C we describe three critical data flows that can run over a PsPIN unit. Flow 1 (*inbound flow*) moves data from the NIC inbound engine to the L2 packet memory and, from there, to the L1 memory of the processing cluster where the packet has been assigned. Moving packet data to L1 memories is not always needed. For example, a handler might only use the packet header (e.g., filtering), the packet header plus a small part of the packet payload (e.g., handlers looking at application-specific headers), or they might not need packet data at all (e.g., packet counting). Applications specify the number of bytes that handlers need for each packet. Flows 2 and 3 move data from PsPIN to the outbound interfaces, namely the NIC outbound (*outbound NIC flow*) and the host interface through PCIe (*outbound host flow*). They are generated by the handlers, which can issue commands to move data to the NIC or to the host. Handlers do not necessarily issue commands as they can directly consume data and communicate results to

Fig. 8. PsPIN maximum throughput.

the host once the message processing finishes: e.g., handlers performing data reductions on the NIC, letting the completion handler write data to the host.

Inbound flow. We measure the throughput PsPIN can sustain for the inbound flow. We measure it as function of the frequency of the completion notifications received by the MPQ engine and the packet size. Figure 8 (left) shows the throughput for handlers executing different number of instructions (x-axis) and for different packet sizes (i.e., 64 B, 512 B, and 1024 B packets). We also include: (1) the maximum throughput that the PsPIN can achieve: this is the minimum between the interconnect bandwidth and the cumulative bandwidth offered by the 32 HPUs when executing x instructions; and (2) the throughput for misaligned packets (i.e., packet size + 1 byte). We let each handler execute x integer arithmetic instructions, each completed in a single cycle. The x-axis can also be read as handler duration in nanoseconds. The data shows how PsPIN can schedule aligned packets at the maximum available bandwidth and the HPU runtime introduces minimum overhead (i.e., 8 cycles per packet, see Section IV-B1).

Figure 8 (right) shows the maximum number of HPUs that are utilized when running handlers executing x instructions, for different packet sizes. PsPIN can schedule one 64 B packet per cycle. Even with empty handlers, we need 19 HPUs to process them because of the overhead necessary to invoke the handlers. With bigger packets, the time budget increases: handlers with small instruction counts can process 512 B and 1024 B packets at full throughput with a single HPU.

Inbound + outbound flows. We now study the throughput offered when packets are received and sent out of PsPIN. The execution context is configured to move the full packet to L1. For testing the outbound NIC flow, we develop handlers performing a UDP ping-pong: they swap source and destination IPs and UDP ports, then issue a NIC command to send it back over the network. Overall, this handler consists of 27 instructions (20 for the swap and 7 for the issuing the command). The handlers for the outbound host flow only issue a DMA command to move the packet to the host, without modifying it. Figure 9 shows both the cases in which the packet is sent from L1 and from the L2 packet buffer.

Fig. 9. Moving data out of PsPIN.

The L2 packet buffer, with its 32 512-bit-wide banks, is optimized for wide accesses, as the ones performed by the DMA engines of the involved units. The L1 TCDM is

Fig. 10. Handler throughput on PsPIN for different packet sizes.

optimized for serving 32-bit word accesses from the HPUs and organized in 64 32-bit-wide banks. This difference shows up in the throughput and it is caused by a higher number of bank conflicts in the data-from-L1 case: with 64 B packets, both the outbound flows hardly reach 200 Gbit/s when reading from L1, while 400 Gbit/s is reached when reading data from the L2. For bigger packets (≥ 512 B), the time budget is large enough to allow also the L1 case to reach full bandwidth.

C. Handlers Characterization

To evaluate the performance of PsPIN for realistic packet handlers, we select a set of use cases ranging from packet steering to full message processing. We first show the throughput they can achieve on PsPIN, then we measure the per-core throughput achievable on PsPIN RISC-V and compare it to the one achieved on more complex and powerful, but bigger, architectures such as x86 and ARM. This comparison aims to analyze costs and benefits of employing more complex architectures for packet processing and to motivate our design choice of employing simple RISC-V cores as HPUs. We simulate a network with zero inter-packet-delay, in order to not make our results network-bound and show the maximum achievable throughput. The considered use cases are:

Data reduction. Reducing data of multiple messages is a core operation of collective reductions [38] and one-sided accumulations [29]. Given n messages, each carrying m data items of type t , this operation computes an array of m entries of type t where entry i is the reduction of the i -th data item across the n messages. We benchmark an instance of this use case (named *reduce*) with 512 packet, each carrying 512 32-bit integers. Payload handlers accumulate data in L1 using the sum operator. The completion handler informs the host that the result is available with a direct host write command.

Data aggregation. Utilized in, e.g., data-mining applications [34], this operation consists in accumulating the data items carried by a message. This benchmark (*aggregate*) uses a 1 MiB message of 32-bit integers that are summed up in L1. The completion handler copies the aggregate to host memory.

Packet filtering/rewriting. Typical of intrusion-detection, traffic monitoring, and packet sniffing systems [18]. For each packet, it queries an application-defined hash table (in L2) by using the source IP address (32-bit) as key. If a match is found, the UDP destination port is overwritten with the matched value and written to host memory. This benchmark, named *filtering*, uses 512 messages and a hash table of 65,536 entries.

Key-Value cache. A key-value store (*kvstore*) cache on the NIC. The cache is stored in L2 and is implemented as a set-associative cache to limit the L2 accesses needed to maintain the cache (e.g., eviction victims are chosen within a row).

Fig. 11. Per-core handler throughput: ARM vs x86 vs RISC-V.

We generate a YCSB [17] workload of 1,000 requests (50/50 read/write ratio, $\theta=1.1$). The cache associativity is set to 4 and the total number of entries is set to 500. The set is determined as the key (32-bit integer) modulo the number of sets.

Scatter. This use case (*strided_ddt*) models data transfers that are copied to the destination memory according to a receiver-specified memory layout [38], [20]. This benchmark sends a 1 MiB message that is copied to host memory in blocks of 256 bytes and with a stride of 512 bytes. The layout description (i.e., block size and stride) is stored in L2.

Histogram. Given a set of messages, it summarizes data items by value. This application is common in distributed join algorithms [10]. In our instance, we receive 512 messages, each carrying 512 integers randomly generated in the $[0, 1024]$ interval. The handlers count how many data items per value have been received and finally copy the histogram to the host.

1) *Handler Throughput:* Figure 10 shows the throughput achieved by the considered handlers on PsPIN for different packet sizes. We observe that PsPIN achieves 400 Gbit/s for *filtering*, *kvstore*, and *strided_ddt* already for 512 B packets. In the other cases, handlers are compute-intensive, and they operate on every 32-bit word of each received packet. Nonetheless, PsPIN achieves more than 200 Gbit/s, which the state-of-the-art network speed, from 512 B packets. Thanks to the modularity of this architecture (S8), a scenario where 400 Gbit/s must be sustained also for this type of workload can be satisfied by doubling the number of processing clusters.

2) *RISC-V vs x86 vs ARM:* This set of experiments outlines the benefits of adopting a simple, RISC-V-based architecture over more powerful and complex ones, such as x86 and ARM. We select two representative architectures, showing not only the effects of different CPU types but also of different memory subsystem configurations (e.g., caches vs scratchpads):

- **ault** 18-core 64-bit 2-way SMT, 4-way superscalar, out-of-order-execution Intel Skylake Xeon Gold 6154 (3 GHz).
- **zynq** Xilinx Zynq ZU9EG MPSoC featuring a quad-core ARM Cortex-A53 (64-bit 2-way superscalar at 1.2 GHz).

To run on these architectures, we develop a benchmark that loads a predefined list of packets in memory, spawns a set of worker threads, and statically assigns the packets to the workers. This setting can be compared to an ideal DPDK execution since the packets are already in memory and the workers do not experience any DPDK-related overheads (e.g., polling device ports, copying bursts in local buffer). If not otherwise specified, the packet size is set to 1 KiB.

Figure 11 (left) compares the per-core throughput of each architecture, which is computed as function of the median handler completion time when using a number of worker

Fig. 12. Handlers performance on different architectures. For zynq and ault, we show the cases with one and four worker threads. The upper and lower whiskers of the boxplot represent $Q3 + 1.5 \cdot IQR$ and $Q1 - 1.5 \cdot IQR$ (Q_i : i -th quartile; IQR : inter-quartile range), respectively.

threads equal to the number of available cores. Despite the fact that this comparison is disadvantageous for PsPIN because it is the one potentially experiencing the most memory contention with its 32 cores, PsPIN shows better per-core throughput over the best competitor for *histogram* (1.3x), *kvstore* (1.9x), and *reduce* (5.3x). For less memory-bound workloads, the more powerful cores of ault and zynq outperform PsPIN by up to 1.8x for *aggregate*, 40x for *filtering*, and 36x for *strided_ddt*.

However, comparing the per-core throughput without factoring in the area of each architecture is not fair (e.g., ault is 26x larger than PsPIN). Table IV summarizes area estimates and shows the scaled area per processing element (*Area/PE (scaled)*), which is the area per processing element (*Area/PE*) scaled to the same production process (22 nm) and same amount of memory per PE. Figure 11 (right) reports the throughput normalized to the scaled area for the considered architectures. PsPIN is up to 10.7x more area-efficient than zynq (minimum: 2.6x for *strided_ddt*) and up to 248x more area-efficient than ault (minimum: 1.5x for *filtering*) on all considered workloads. We conclude that, while it is expected that more powerful architectures achieve higher raw throughput for compute-intensive workloads, PsPIN provides better area efficiency and can sustain line rate while fully offloading packet processing to the NIC and freeing CPU resources.

Arch.	Tech.	Die area	PEs	Memory	Area/PE	Area/PE (scaled)
ault	14 nm	485 mm ² [4]	18	43.3 MiB	17.978 mm ²	35.956 mm ²
zynq	16 nm	3.27 mm ² [3]	4	1.125 MiB	0.876 mm ²	1.752 mm ²
PsPIN	22 nm	18.5 mm ²	32	12 MiB	0.578 mm ²	0.578 mm ²

TABLE IV
ARCHITECTURAL CHARACTERISTICS. PE: PROCESSING ELEMENT

To gain more insights on the performance characteristics of the selected handlers, Figure 12 shows a set of performance metrics as measured on the considered architectures. We report handlers' execution times, number of executed instructions, MIPS (*million instructions per second*), and cache misses. For PsPIN, L1 misses represent the number of accesses to either remote L1s or L2. For ault and zynq, performance is measured with CPU hardware counters [54]. To show the effects of

resource contention, we run experiments with a single worker thread (i.e., no contention) and with four workers in parallel.

For most of the considered use cases, running times on PsPIN are not more than 2x the best case (i.e., no contention) of other architectures. The worst case is *filtering*, which computes a hash function on an 8-byte value, resulting in a compute-intensive task that allows ault to run this handler more than 30x times faster than PsPIN. In general, for workloads that mainly execute arithmetic instructions (e.g., *aggregate* and *filtering*) or do not frequently access shared or packet memory (e.g., *strided_ddt*), ault outperforms zynq and PsPIN in terms of completion time. For example, on ault, the compiler optimizes *aggregate* by using SIMD packed integer instructions. However, as shown in Figure 11, this difference does not take into account the larger area occupied by this architecture. Even though PsPIN has a simpler architecture than ault and zynq, it still competes in overall execution time for the other cases due to the comparable rate of executed instructions per second (MIPS), which is influenced by higher L1 miss rates on ault and zynq (see *histogram*, *kvstore*, and *reduce*). In PsPIN, packets are copied directly into the L1 of the cluster where the handler is executed, enabling single-cycle access. Also, PsPIN has no hardware caches, hence it does not suffer from cache-line ping-pong scenarios, as observed on other architectures for, e.g., *histogram* and *reduce*. RISC-V AMOs [59] enable single-cycle atomic operations that can save up to 3x instructions over other implementations (e.g., linked load, store conditional) for the *reduce* and *histogram* cases.

V. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

The PsPIN configuration and analysis that we show in this work is aimed at sustaining a 400 Gbit/s line rate. *How can PsPIN be scaled out to sustain higher bandwidths?* To reason about scaling we need to consider how to scale memories, interconnects, and cores and how this affects power and area. We identify two types of memories: the packet buffer, the size of which depends on the network bandwidth and the time packets spend in PsPIN (i.e., the packet latency), and

the handler memory, the size of which depends on the specific handlers that are offloaded (e.g., to store their state). Note that the second class does not depend on the network bandwidth.

Fig. 13. Packet buffer size over packet latencies and line rates. Horizontal lines are min, geometric mean, and max handler running times among the ones of Figure 12. Points indicate handler critical times (HCT) after which handlers are bottlenecks for a given packet-size/line-rate/number-of-cores combination.

In Figure 13 we use Little’s law to determine the packet buffer size over different packet latencies (x-axis) and line rates (200 Gbit/s, 400 Gbit/s, and 800 Gbit/s). The packet latency is the time from when a packet arrives in PsPIN to when it is processed and can be freed up from the packet buffer. As we show in Section IV-B1, the time needed to schedule a handler processing a given packet ranges from 26 ns for 64 B packets to 40 ns for 1024 B ones. For simplicity, we do not take into account the scheduling latency in the following discussion but only the handler execution time. Figure 13 further shows the minimum, maximum, and the geometric mean for all handlers of Section IV-C. We notice how, even for an 800 Gbit/s network and packet latencies of 3 us, the required packet buffer capacity is only 300 KiB. Currently, PsPIN provides a 4 MiB packet buffer that would be enough to sustain even higher line rate or packet latencies. Moreover, we need to take into account that handlers should terminate within a threshold in order to not bottleneck the incoming data flow, constraining the packet buffer size. We plot the handler critical times (HCT) that are thresholds after which handlers become bottlenecks for given combination of packet size, line rate, and core count. HCTs are computed by scaling the number of cores together with the line rate. We show HCTs for 256 B, 1024 B, and 4096 B packets. In Section IV-A, we show how memories take a large portion of both area (87%) and power (52%). Since the memories provided in this configuration are partially independent from the network bandwidth (i.e., handler memory) and partially over-provisioned (i.e., packet buffer), we expect area and power to remain stable while scaling PsPIN to sustain higher line rates.

The modular organization of PsPIN allows to scale up the number of processing clusters (**S8**) for, e.g., enabling higher workloads (i.e., longer handlers) without becoming a bottleneck. However, to increase the sustained network bandwidth, we would either need to re-balance the system in order to feed the processing clusters at line rate (e.g., to sustain 1 Tbit/s, we should adopt 1024-bit data paths), or have multiple PsPIN accelerators with an additional scheduling level.

In the near future, we plan to investigate a possible integration of Snitch [61] cores and clusters in PsPIN. With simpler RISC-V cores, a more flexible cluster architecture,

and virtual memory support, we believe this integration can further improve area and power efficiency, and increase the flexibility of the proposed in-network compute accelerator. Additionally, we are following a line of research aimed at evaluating the costs and benefits of having PsPIN integrated into network switches, which would enable general packet processing deeper in the network.

VI. RELATED WORK

One of the oldest concepts related to PsPIN is Active Messages (AM) [56]. However, in the AM model, messages are atomic and can be processed only once they are fully received. In sPIN, the processing happens at the packets level, leading to lower latencies and buffer requirements.

sPIN is closely related to systems such as P4 [13], which allow users to define match-action rules on a per-packet basis and are supported by switch architectures such as AMT [14], FlexPipe [41], and Cavium’s Xplaint. Those architectures target switches and work on packet headers, not packet data. FlexNIC [32] extends this idea by introducing modifiable memory and enabling fine-grained steering of DMA streams at the receiver NIC. These extensions can be used for, e.g., partition the key-space of a key-value store and steer requests to specific cores. However, the offloading of complex application-specific tasks (e.g., datatype processing [20]) has not been demonstrated in this programming model. In contrast, PsPIN allows offloading of arbitrary functions executed on general-purpose processing cores with small hardware extensions to increase throughput and reduce latency. PANIC [36] is a recent work sharing many design principles of PsPIN. The main difference is that PsPIN allows applications to define handlers to be executed on incoming packets while PANIC enables them to express compositions of pre-offloaded tasks.

Programmable NICs are not new. Quadrics QsNet employed them to accelerate collectives [60] and to implement early versions of Portals [42]. Myrinet NICs [57] allowed users to offload modules written in C to the specialized NIC cores. Modern approaches to NIC offload [51], [21] requires network engineers to implement functionalities as FPGA modules, while PsPIN uses easier to (re-)program RISC-V cores. Differently from these approaches, sPIN enables user-space applications to define their own C/C++ packet handlers.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Processing data in the network is a necessary step to scale applications along with the network speeds. This work defines principles and architectural characteristics of packet processing engines, which are the next step after RDMA acceleration. We propose PsPIN, a power and area efficient RISC-V based unit implementing the sPIN programming model, defining the interfaces for NIC integration. We evaluate PsPIN, showing that it can process packets at up to 400 Gbit/s line rate and motivate our architectural choices with a performance study of a set of example handlers over different architectures. PsPIN is an open-source project and is available at:

<https://github.com/spcl/pspin>

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REFERENCES

- [1] Broadcom Stingray SmartNIC. <https://www.broadcom.com/products/ethernet-connectivity/smartnic>. Accessed: 2020-18-03.
- [2] Mellanox BlueField SmartNIC. <https://www.mellanox.com/products/bluefield-overview>. Accessed: 2020-18-03.
- [3] Wikichip.org: Cortex-A53 - microarchitectures - ARM. https://en.wikichip.org/wiki/arm_holdings/microarchitectures/cortex-a53. Accessed: 2020-15-04.
- [4] Wikichip.org: Skylake (server) - microarchitectures - Intel. [https://en.wikichip.org/wiki/intel/microarchitectures/skylake_\(server\)](https://en.wikichip.org/wiki/intel/microarchitectures/skylake_(server)). Accessed: 2020-15-04.
- [5] XC Series GNI and DMAPP API user guide. <https://pubs.cray.com/content/S-2446/CLE%207.0.UP01/xtm-series-gni-and-dmapp-api-user-guide>. Accessed: 2020-18-03.
- [6] Bob Alverson, Edwin Froese, Larry Kaplan, and Duncan Roweth. Cray XC series network. *Cray Inc., White Paper WP-Aries 01-1112*, 2012.
- [7] Robert Alverson, Duncan Roweth, and Larry Kaplan. The gemini system interconnect. In *2010 18th IEEE Symposium on High Performance Interconnects*, pages 83–87. IEEE, 2010.
- [8] Michael Attig and Gordon Brebner. 400 Gb/s programmable packet parsing on a single FPGA. In *2011 ACM/IEEE Seventh Symposium on Architectures for Networking and Communications Systems*, pages 12–23. IEEE, 2011.
- [9] B. W Barrett, R. Brightwell, S. Hemmert, K. Pedretti, K. Wheeler, K. Underwood, R. Riessen, T. Hoefler, A. B Maccabe, and T. Hudson. The Portals 4.2 network programming interface. *Sandia National Laboratories, November 2012, Technical Report SAND2012-10087*, 2018.
- [10] Claude Barthels, Ingo Müller, Timo Schneider, Gustavo Alonso, and Torsten Hoefler. Distributed join algorithms on thousands of cores. *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment*, 10(5), 2017.
- [11] Tarick Bedeir. Building an RDMA-capable application with IB Verbs. *Technical report, HPC Advisory Council*, 2010.
- [12] Mike Belshe, Roberto Peon, and Martin Thomson. Hypertext transfer protocol version 2 (HTTP/2), 2015.
- [13] Pat Bosshart, Dan Daly, Glen Gibb, Martin Izzard, Nick McKeown, Jennifer Rexford, Cole Schlesinger, Dan Talayco, Amin Vahdat, George Varghese, et al. P4: Programming protocol-independent packet processors. *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review*, 44(3):87–95, 2014.
- [14] Pat Bosshart, Glen Gibb, Hun-Seok Kim, George Varghese, Nick McKeown, Martin Izzard, Fernando Mujica, and Mark Horowitz. Forwarding metamorphosis: Fast programmable match-action processing in hardware for SDN. *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review*, 43(4):99–110, 2013.
- [15] Marco Spaziani Brunella, Giacomo Belocchi, Marco Bonola, Salvatore Pontarelli, Giuseppe Siracusano, Giuseppe Bianchi, Aniello Cammarano, Alessandro Palumbo, Luca Petrucci, and Roberto Bifulco. hXDP: Efficient software packet processing on FPGA NICs. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.14145*, 2020.
- [16] Darius Buntinas, Dhaleswar K Panda, and Ponnuswamy Sadayappan. Fast NIC-based barrier over Myrinet/GM. In *Proceedings 15th International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium. IPDPS 2001*, pages 8–pp. IEEE, 2000.
- [17] Brian F Cooper, Adam Silberstein, Erwin Tam, Raghu Ramakrishnan, and Russell Sears. Benchmarking cloud serving systems with YCSB. In *Proceedings of the 1st ACM symposium on Cloud computing*, pages 143–154, 2010.
- [18] Luca Deri. High-speed dynamic packet filtering. *Journal of Network and Systems Management*, 15(3):401–415, 2007.
- [19] Saïd Derradji, Thibaut Palfer-Sollier, Jean-Pierre Panziera, Axel Poudes, and François Wellenreiter Atos. The BXI interconnect architecture. In *2015 IEEE 23rd Annual Symposium on High-Performance Interconnects*, pages 18–25. IEEE, 2015.
- [20] Salvatore Di Girolamo, Konstantin Taranov, Andreas Kurth, Michael Schaffner, Timo Schneider, Jakub Beránek, Maciej Besta, Luca Benini, Duncan Roweth, and Torsten Hoefler. Network-accelerated non-contiguous memory transfers. In *Proceedings of the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis, SC '19*, New York, NY, USA, 2019. Association for Computing Machinery.
- [21] Haggai Eran, Lior Zeno, Maroun Tork, Gabi Malka, and Mark Silberstein. NICA: An infrastructure for inline acceleration of network applications. In *2019 USENIX Annual Technical Conference (USENIX ATC 19)*, pages 345–362, 2019.
- [22] Daniel Firestone, Andrew Putnam, Sambhrama Mundkur, Derek Chiou, Alireza Dabagh, Mike Andrewartha, Hari Angepat, Vivek Bhanu, Adrian Caulfield, Eric Chung, et al. Azure accelerated networking: SmartNICs in the public cloud. In *15th USENIX Symposium on Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI 18)*, pages 51–66, 2018.
- [23] Michael Gautschi, Pasquale Davide Schiavone, Andreas Traber, Igor Loi, Antonio Pullini, Davide Rossi, Eric Flamand, Frank K Gürkaynak, and Luca Benini. Near-threshold RISC-V core with DSP extensions for scalable IoT endpoint devices. *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, 25(10):2700–2713, 2017.
- [24] Richard L Graham, Devendar Bureddy, Pak Lui, Hal Rosenstock, Gilad Shainer, Gil Bloch, Dror Goldener, Mike Dubman, Sasha Kotchubievsky, Vladimir Koushnr, et al. Scalable hierarchical aggregation protocol (SHArP): a hardware architecture for efficient data reduction. In *2016 First International Workshop on Communication Optimizations in HPC (COMHPC)*, pages 1–10. IEEE, 2016.
- [25] Richard L Graham, Steve Poole, Pavel Shamis, Gil Bloch, Noam Bloch, Hillel Chapman, Michael Kagan, Ariel Shahar, Ishai Rabinovitz, and Gilad Shainer. ConnectX-2 InfiniBand management queues: First investigation of the new support for network offloaded collective operations. In *2010 10th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing*, pages 53–62. IEEE, 2010.
- [26] Frank K Gürkaynak, Robert Schilling, Michael Muehlberghuber, Francesco Conti, Stefan Mangard, and Luca Benini. Multi-core data analytics SoC with a flexible 1.76 Gbit/s AES-XTS cryptographic accelerator in 65 nm CMOS. In *Proceedings of the Fourth Workshop on Cryptography and Security in Computing Systems*, pages 19–24, 2017.
- [27] Jim Handy. *The cache memory book*. Morgan Kaufmann, 1998.
- [28] Torsten Hoefler, Salvatore Di Girolamo, Konstantin Taranov, Ryan E. Grant, and Ron Brightwell. sPIN: High-performance streaming processing in the network. In *Proceedings of the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis, SC '17*, New York, NY, USA, 2017. Association for Computing Machinery.
- [29] Torsten Hoefler, James Dinan, Rajeev Thakur, Brian Barrett, Pavan Balaji, William Gropp, and Keith Underwood. Remote memory access programming in MPI-3. *ACM Transactions on Parallel Computing (TOPC)*, 2(2):1–26, 2015.
- [30] InfiniBand Trade Association et al. InfiniBand architecture specification release 1.2. <http://www.infinibandta.org>, 2000.
- [31] Jana Iyengar and Martin Thomson. QUIC: A UDP-based multiplexed and secure transport. *Internet Engineering Task Force, Internet-Draft draftietf-quic-transport-17*, 2018.
- [32] Antoine Kaufmann, Simon Peter, Naveen Kr Sharma, Thomas Anderson, and Arvind Krishnamurthy. High performance packet processing with FlexNIC. In *ACM SIGARCH Computer Architecture News*, volume 44, pages 67–81. ACM, 2016.
- [33] Jakub Kicinski and Nicolaas Viljoen. eBPF hardware offload to SmartNICs: clsbpf and XDP.
- [34] V Pradeep Kumar and RV Krishnaiah. Horizontal aggregations in SQL to prepare data sets for data mining analysis. *IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering (IOSRJCE)*, pages 2278–0661, 2012.
- [35] Andreas Kurth, Wolfgang Rönninger, Thomas Benz, Matheus Cavalcante, Fabian Schuiki, Florian Zaruba, and Luca Benini. An open-source platform for high-performance non-coherent on-chip communication. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.05334*, 2020.
- [36] Jiaxin Lin, Kiran Patel, Brent E Stephens, Anirudh Sivaraman, and Aditya Akella. PANIC: A high-performance programmable NIC for multi-tenant networks. In *14th USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation (OSDI 20)*, pages 243–259, 2020.

- [37] Hugh T Mair, Gordon Gammie, Alice Wang, Rolf Lagerquist, CJ Chung, Sumanth Gururajarao, Ping Kao, Anand Rajagopalan, Anirban Saha, Amit Jain, et al. A 20nm 2.5 GHz ultra-low-power tri-cluster CPU subsystem with adaptive power allocation for optimal mobile SoC performance. In *2016 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference (ISSCC)*, pages 76–77. IEEE, 2016.
- [38] Message Passing Interface Forum. MPI: A message-passing interface standard version 3.0, 09 2012. Chapter author for Collective Communication, Process Topologies, and One Sided Communications.
- [39] Sebastiano Miano, Matteo Bertrone, Fulvio Risso, Massimo Tumolo, and Mauricio Vásquez Bernal. Creating complex network services with eBPF: Experience and lessons learned. In *2018 IEEE 19th International Conference on High Performance Switching and Routing (HPSR)*, pages 1–8. IEEE, 2018.
- [40] John Nickolls, Ian Buck, Michael Garland, and Kevin Skadron. Scalable parallel programming with CUDA. *Queue*, 6(2):40–53, 2008.
- [41] Recep Ozdag. Intel® Ethernet switch FM6000 series - software defined networking. See goo.gl/AnvOvX, 5, 2012.
- [42] Ron Brightwell Kevin T Pedretti and Ron Brightwell. A NIC-offload implementation of Portals for Quadrics QsNet. In *Fifth LCI International Conference on Linux Clusters*, 2004.
- [43] Fabrizio Petrini, Salvador Coll, Eitan Frachtenberg, and Adolfo Hoisie. Hardware-and software-based collective communication on the Quadrics network. In *Proceedings IEEE International Symposium on Network Computing and Applications. NCA 2001*, pages 24–35. IEEE, 2001.
- [44] Salvatore Pontarelli, Roberto Bifulco, Marco Bonola, Carmelo Cascone, Marco Spaziani, Valerio Bruschi, Davide Sanvito, Giuseppe Siracusano, Antonio Capone, Michio Honda, et al. Flowblaze: Stateful packet processing in hardware. In *16th USENIX Symposium on Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI 19)*, pages 531–548, 2019.
- [45] Jungyul Pyo, Youngmin Shin, Hoi-Jin Lee, Sung-il Bae, Min-su Kim, Kwangil Kim, Ken Shin, Yohan Kwon, Heungchul Oh, Jaeyoung Lim, et al. A 20nm high-K metal-gate heterogeneous 64b quad-core CPUs and hexa-core GPU for high-performance and energy-efficient mobile application processor. In *2015 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference-(ISSCC) Digest of Technical Papers*, pages 1–3. IEEE, 2015.
- [46] R Rajesh, Kannan Babu Ramia, and Muralidhar Kulkarni. Integration of LwIP stack over Intel DPDK for high throughput packet delivery to applications. In *2014 Fifth International Symposium on Electronic System Design*, pages 130–134. IEEE, 2014.
- [47] Kadangode Ramakrishnan, Sally Floyd, David Black, et al. The addition of explicit congestion notification (ECN) to IP. 2001.
- [48] Davide Rossi, Francesco Conti, Andrea Marongiu, Antonio Pullini, Igor Loi, Michael Gautschi, Giuseppe Tagliavini, Alessandro Capotondi, Philippe Flatresse, and Luca Benini. PULP: A parallel ultra low power platform for next generation IoT applications. In *2015 IEEE Hot Chips 27 Symposium (HCS)*, pages 1–39. IEEE, 2015.
- [49] Whit Schonbein, Ryan E Grant, Matthew GF Dosanjh, and Dorian Arnold. INCA: in-network compute assistance. In *Proceedings of the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis*, pages 1–13, 2019.
- [50] Daniele De Sensi, Salvatore Di Girolamo, Kim H. McMahon, Duncan Roweth, and Torsten Hoefler. An in-depth analysis of the Slingshot interconnect, 2020.
- [51] David Sidler, Zeke Wang, Monica Chiosa, Amit Kulkarni, and Gustavo Alonso. StRoM: smart remote memory. In *Proceedings of the Fifteenth European Conference on Computer Systems*, pages 1–16, 2020.
- [52] John E Stone, David Gohara, and Guochun Shi. OpenCL: A parallel programming standard for heterogeneous computing systems. *Computing in science & engineering*, 12(3):66–73, 2010.
- [53] Viswanath Subramanian, Michael R Krause, and Ramesh VelurEunni. Remote direct memory access (RDMA) completion, August 14 2012. US Patent 8,244,825.
- [54] Dan Terpstra, Heike Jagode, Haihang You, and Jack Dongarra. Collecting performance data with PAPI-C. In *Tools for High Performance Computing 2009*, pages 157–173. Springer, 2010.
- [55] Andreas Traber, Florian Zaruba, Sven Stucki, Antonio Pullini, Germain Haugou, Eric Flamand, Frank K Gurkaynak, and Luca Benini. PULPino: A small single-core RISC-V SoC. In *3rd RISC-V Workshop*, 2016.
- [56] Thorsten Von Eicken, David E Culler, Seth Copen Goldstein, and Klaus Erik Schauer. Active messages: a mechanism for integrated communication and computation. *ACM SIGARCH Computer Architecture News*, 20(2):256–266, 1992.
- [57] Adam Wagner, Hyun-Wook Jin, Dhableswar K Panda, and Rolf Riesen. NIC-based offload of dynamic user-defined modules for Myrinet clusters. In *2004 IEEE International Conference on Cluster Computing (IEEE Cat. No. 04EX935)*, pages 205–214. IEEE, 2004.
- [58] Andrew Waterman, Yunsup Lee, Rimantas Avizienis, David A Patterson, and Krste Asanović. The RISC-V instruction set manual volume II: Privileged architecture version 1.9. *EECS Department, University of California, Berkeley, Tech. Rep. UCB/EECS-2016-129*, 2016.
- [59] Andrew Waterman, Yunsup Lee, David Patterson, Krste Asanovic, and Volume I User level Isa. The RISC-V instruction set manual. *Volume I: User-Level ISA*, version, 2, 2014.
- [60] Weikuan Yu, Darius Buntinas, Richard L Graham, and Dhableswar K Panda. Efficient and scalable barrier over Quadrics and Myrinet with a new NIC-based collective message passing protocol. In *18th International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium, 2004. Proceedings.*, page 182. IEEE, 2004.
- [61] Florian Zaruba, Fabian Schuiki, Torsten Hoefler, and Luca Benini. Snitch: A tiny pseudo dual-issue processor for area and energy efficient execution of floating-point intensive workloads. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 2020.